

Ratoon grain yield (t/ha)

Relationship between ratoon rating and ratoon grain yield in 22 rice cultivars. ACRI, Tamil Nadu, India, 1987 wet season.

The association between RR and ratoon yield was positive and significant (see figure). Most cultivars with high RR had high ratoon yield. RR can be used as a criterion in selecting rice cultivars for high ratooning ability. ■

Effect of leaf senescence and stubble carbohydrate content on ratoon rice yield

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We studied the relationship between carbohydrate content in the stubble and leaf senescence at main harvest and ratoon yield in rice genotypes Bhavani, MDU3, IET6262, IET6709, IET7552, and IET9235 and their crosses during Oct 1988.

Each entry was planted in two 2-m-long rows at 20- × 10-cm spacing, in a randomized block design with three replications. Recommended practices were followed for both main and ratoon crops. Ten randomly selected plants of each parent and cross from each replication were used to estimate main crop stubble carbohydrate content, leaf senescence, and ratoon yield.

Total carbohydrate content was estimated by phenol sulfuric acid method. Leaf senescence was estimated by

$$\% \text{ senescent} = \frac{\text{Total number senescent leaves}}{\text{Total number green leaves at milk stage}} \times 100$$

Relationship of carbohydrate content in stubble and leaf senescence at harvest to ratoon yield^a Madurai, India 1988.

Parent, cross	Carbohydrate content of stubble (%)	Leaf senescence (%)	Ratoon yield (g/10 plants)
Bhavani	20.5	55.2	14.4
MDU3	17.8	51.4	12.3
IET6262	21.2	57.6	12.8
IET6709	23.2	52.9	13.6
IET7552	18.8	60.8	15.1
IET9239	24.2	59.6	11.7
Bhavani/MDU3	18.6 (18.2)	54.0 (53.4)	14.5 (12.5)
Bhavani/IET6262	21.2 (19.4)	54.9 (54.2)	16.1 (13.2)
Bhavani/IET6729	20.7 (19.7)	51.2 (58.0)	15.4 (15.1)
Bhavani/IET7552	19.7 (20.9)	66.3 (58.7)	14.9 (16.3)
Bhavani/IET9239	20.6 (22.0)	55.0 (58.2)	14.3 (12.8)
MDU3/IET6262	17.6 (16.7)	52.0 (56.3)	12.8 (13.5)
MDU3/IET6709	20.2 (21.5)	51.4 (50.4)	13.1 (13.7)
MDU3/IET7552	17.8 (16.7)	51.7 (56.0)	12.4 (15.0)
MDU3/IET9239	19.4 (21.2)	56.8 (66.3)	12.5 (11.9)
IET6262/IET6709	22.0 (23.8)	58.4 (56.2)	14.4 (15.2)
IET6262/IET7552	17.5 (19.0)	62.2 (60.1)	13.0 (15.1)
IET6262/IET9239	21.7 (25.2)	52.9 (58.5)	12.8 (12.5)
IET6709/IET7552	20.7 (22.3)	56.5 (55.2)	15.2 (16.8)
IET6709/IET9239	24.8 (23.8)	52.5 (54.9)	13.5 (12.6)
IET7552/IET9239	22.6 (20.2)	62.5 (56.5)	15.9 (12.0)
Mean: Parent	20.95	56.26	13.32
cross	20.52	55.71	13.96
SE	0.43	0.94	0.28
LSD (P = 0.05)	1.22	2.65	0.78
Correlation with ratoon yield	0.0137 ^{ns}	0.2136 ^{ns}	

^aFigures in parentheses are for reciprocal cross.

IET7552 and Bhavani had the highest ratoon yields (see table). The effects of carbohydrate content of the stubble and leaf senescence at harvest on ratoon yield

were not significant, indicating low influence of these factors on ratoon yield. This emphasizes the importance of inherent ratooning ability of parents. ■

Effect of high humidity and low temperature on spikelet fertility in indica rice

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Rains, high humidity, and low temperature lower spikelet fertility in first crop indica rice and could increase percentage of empty spikelets and reduce yields. We studied the effect of such wet weather on 12 indica varieties in 1989.

Spikelet fertility percentage (SFP) was measured on 6-10 randomly selected panicles at heading. SFP was reduced with increased humidity and decreased temperature (see figure). The most important meteorological factor was relative humidity ($r = -0.96^*$), followed by mean temperature 3 d after heading.

Response of 3 groups of indica varieties to relative humidity and daily mean temperature at heading and flowering. Hangzhou, China, 1989.